

Potential of Biocrude Production from Camel Manure via Hydrothermal Liquefaction: A Qatar Case Study

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Abstract

Livestock manure is a significant contributor to methane emissions which are released upon the decomposition of manure under anaerobic conditions. Besides, the mismanagement of manure may lead to serious water and soil contamination. In Qatar, camels are commonly domesticated for their meat and milk. Its camel population generates around 120,000 tonnes of manure annually, resulting in nearly 4 kilotonnes of CO₂ eq emissions. Meanwhile, Hydrothermal Liquefaction (HTL) has emerged as a promising technology for the valorization of wet wastes, as it does not require the energy-intensive drying step as in gasification and pyrolysis technologies. As such, this study investigates the potential of biocrude production from camel manure in Qatar, and potentially other similar areas, using HTL. Proximate and elemental analysis of manure samples is conducted, while the process is simulated using Aspen Plus® software with an optimal feed capacity to completely utilize most of Qatar's camel manure. Moreover, an economic assessment is conducted using Aspen Process Economic Analyzer (APEA). The demonstrated results are encouraging; whereby, a biocrude yield of 37.9% (dry, ash-free basis) is achieved, with a minimum selling price of 72 US\$/bbl. Nevertheless, the presence of well-established oil refineries in Qatar makes it feasible to upgrade biocrude into drop-in transportation fuels via co-processing with petroleum crude, which has been recently certified by the American Society for Testing and Materials.

Keywords: Hydrothermal Liquefaction, Camel manure, Qatar, Biocrude.

I. Introduction

In Qatar, camels have been long domesticated for their meat, milk and fur. Recently, they have been tamed for racing which is becoming a very popular sport in this part of the world. According to the Planning and Statistics Authority of Qatar, there are around 126,000 camels in Qatar ([Agriculture Statistics, 2018](#)). These camels roughly produce around 120,000 tonnes of manure ([Lensch, 1999](#)), which is responsible for nearly 4 kilotonnes of CO₂ eq ([Sowunmi et al., 2015](#)). Camel manure of such magnitude is often disposed into landfill dumps, which may cause serious degradation and contamination of soil and water resources. Hence, a more efficient approach for the valorization of manure needs to be identified.

Although camel manure can be processed using different thermochemical processes such as pyrolysis and gasification, it is believed that the hydrothermal liquefaction technology (HTL) can better handle high moisture content feedstocks. HTL is a process that converts any carbonaceous material into biocrude oil, making use of hot and high pressurized water. Usually, the process is performed at a temperature between 250 and 400°C, a residence time up to 60 min, an operating pressure ranging between 4 and 25 MPa ([Chen et al., 2019](#)). Along with biocrude, the process also generates an aqueous phase rich liquid product, char and gases. The performance and the outputs of the HTL process are greatly influenced by factors such as temperature, pressure, residence time, feedstock type, nature of solvents and catalysts used ([Al-Ansari et al., 2020](#); [Alherbawi et al., 2021](#)).

Several studies on HTL of different livestock manures have been reported, including cattle dung ([Yin et al., 2010](#)), poultry litter ([Ghanim et al., 2016](#)) and swine manure ([Vardon et al., 2011](#)). However, no studies on HTL of camel manure have been found in literature, as far as the authors are aware. Hence, this study focuses on the HTL of camel manure, with an objective to estimate the biocrude production potential of Qatar using Aspen Plus (V.9) software. Besides, Aspen Process Economic Analyzer (APEA) is employed to conduct a preliminary economic assessment of the implementation of HTL technology in Qatar.

II. Methodology

The fresh camel manure is procured from a local farm in Qatar. The proximate analysis of the manure is conducted using a thermogravimetry analyzer (TA Instruments SDT 650). The analysis is done according to ASTM D7582-12. While the elemental analysis of the manure is performed in (Euro-vector Euro EA 3000) CHN elemental analyzer according to ASTM D 3176 – 89.

Besides, Aspen Plus (V.9) is used to develop the HTL process. The NRTL package is used as a property method, while the camel manure is defined as a non-conventional component based on the proximate and elemental analysis performed in the former experimental step. The manure is simulated in correlation to coal's enthalpy and density built-in characteristics. Char is defined as 100% carbon (C). The developed process flowsheet is shown in Fig. 1. Camel manure is initially processed in a decomposition reactor to convert it into conventional components using a Fortran code adapted from ([Alnouss et al., 2018](#)). A slurry is created by mixing the biomass stream and water, with the presence of a sodium hydroxide alkali catalyst to enhance the possibility of the formation of oil-like products ([Cao et al., 2017](#)). The slurry is then pumped to the HTL reactor.

Block “RGibbs” is used to simulate the main reaction of the HTL process based on the principle of minimizing Gibbs free energy. The reaction is carried out at 300°C and 175 bars. Possible products are defined based on earlier experimental works (Magdeldin et al., 2018; Pedersen et al., 2017). The water content of the slurry is maintained in a sub-critical state at the given operating conditions, which has a lower viscosity and therefore higher solubility of organic compounds. Upon the completion of the reaction, the stream is purified by separating the solids using a solid separator, and splitting the remaining stream into gas, biocrude and aqueous phases using a three-stage flash drum.

Fig. 1: Hydrothermal liquefaction process' flow diagram.

An economic assessment of the process is conducted using Aspen Plus Process Economic Analyzer (APEA) based on the following assumptions:

- 1) Plant lifespan of 30 years.
- 2) Annual feed capacity of 120,000 tonnes (wet basis).
- 3) Startup period of 6 months.

Besides, the flow prices are defined as presented in Table 1, while the utilities' prices in Qatar are considered. The minimum selling price of biocrude is calculated using the following standard leveled cost of fuel (LCOF) formula (International Energy Agency, 2010):

$$LCOF \left(\frac{U.S.\$}{bbl} \right) = \frac{\sum_1^t ((K+O\&M+R)(1+d)^{-t})}{\sum_1^t ((P(1+d)^{-t})} \quad (1)$$

Where, (t) is the plant lifespan, (K) is the annualized capital cost, (O&M) is the annual operating costs, (R) annual materials costs, (P) is the annual biocrude produced in barrels (bbl) and (d) is the discount rate (set at 10%).

Table 1. Raw materials and utility prices.

Item	Price	Unit	Ref.
Camel manure	25 ^a	\$/tonne	-
Sodium Hydroxide	350	\$/tonne	(Alibaba, 2020)
Electricity (for industry)	0.035 ^b	\$/kWh	(Kahrama, 2020)
Water (for industry)	1.479 ^b	\$/m ³	(Kahrama, 2020)

a) Camel manure is free of charge, while estimated handling and transportation charges are considered.

b) Currency conversion is based on the fixed local rate (US\$ 1 = QAR 3.65).

III. Results and discussion

The proximate and elemental analysis of camel manure samples are presented in Table 2. The results indicate high volatile matter and considerable carbon contents.

Regarding the simulation results, the product composition of the HTL process is presented in Fig.2 on a dry and ash-free basis (daf.%) of feedstock. Significant yields of biocrude (37.9%) and hydrochar (19%) are obtained. Besides, the process released a mixture of gases including CO₂, CO, H₂, CH₄ and NH₃, which can be purified into syngas at a later stage. The biocrude yield from camel manure presented in this study is slightly higher than most of other livestock manure reported earlier under similar conditions as presented in Table 3, which is possibly due to higher carbon contents of camel manure.

Table 2. Proximate and elemental analysis of camel manure.

Proximate analysis		Elemental analysis (wt.%)	
Moisture (as received %)	38.00	C	27.83
Fixed carbon (db.%)	12.53	H	1.02
Volatile matter (db.%)	66.25	O	47.75
Ash (db.%)	21.22	N	2.18

Fig. 2: Products distribution of hydrothermal liquefaction (dry and ash-free basis).

Table 3. Biocrude yield of HTL of camel manure (this study) as compared to other livestock manure reported in literature.

Biomass	Camel manure (this study)	Swine manure (Vardon et al., 2011)	Cattle manure (Yin et al., 2010)	Beef manure (Li et al., 2018)	Sheep manure (Li et al., 2018)
Biocrude Yield (daf.%)	37.90%	30.20%	27.97%	20.20%	25.47%

In terms of the product's quality, the characteristics of biocrude are believed to be advantageous over pyrolysis oil in terms of its chemical and physical properties as presented in Table 4. Whereby, the biocrude heating value is close to that of biodiesel, while its boiling point is close to that of gasoline. Moreover, its low oxygen content grants it a high potential to be upgraded into drop-in transportation fuels at mild refining conditions.

Table 4. Physical and chemical properties of biocrude.

Property	Value	Unit
Density @15°C	880	Kg/m ³
Average boiling point	135.6	°C
Average molecular weight	100.6	g/mol
Lower heating value	38	MJ/kg
Specific gravity	0.87	-
H/C ratio	1.68	-
O/C ratio	0.13	-

Table 5 presents a summary of HTL plant's economic assessment. The minimum selling price (MSP) of biocrude is calculated to be nearly US\$ 72.3 per barrel, which is slightly lower than earlier studies (Kirtania, 2018), mainly due to lower utilities' tariff in Qatar for the industrial sector, as well as the lower biomass price and handling charges. The obtained MSP of biocrude can be enhanced if the produced gases are further purified into useful syngas while the biocrude is upgraded into drop-in transportation fuels, which can be a feasible pathway for countries with an established oil-refining infrastructure like Qatar. Whereby, the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) has already certified the co-processing of fossil crude with up to 5 vol.% bio-components (Prussi et al., 2019).

The breakdown of capital and operating costs is presented in Fig. 3. The graphs demonstrate that biomass cost is the major operating cost component, with nearly (47%) of the net costs, followed by utilities (11.2%) and catalysts (10.12%). On the other hand, the purchased equipment cost accounts for the highest share of the capital costs (~40%), followed by equipment setting (11.25%) and contingencies (10%).

Table 5. Summary of plant's economic assessment.

Item	Value
Total capital cost (\$)	14,224,370
Total operating cost (\$/year)	6,431,563
Total raw materials cost (\$/year)	3,651,000
Total utilities cost (\$/year)	720,031
Equipment cost (\$)	5,756,997
Minimum biocrude selling price (US\$/bbl)	72.3

Fig. 3: Breakdown of (a) capital costs, and (b) operating costs.

IV. Conclusions

In this study, camel manure samples have been analyzed in a laboratory, while the HTL processing of the manure has been simulated in Aspen Plus using the HTL plant specifications that corresponds to the Qatari scenario. The results demonstrate a satisfactory biocrude yield of (37.9 daf.%) with a relatively high quality, while its minimum selling price of (72 US\$/bbl) is encouraging.

Although HTL technology still requires further enhancement to be implemented at the industrial scale, it proved to have a high potential to produce higher quality bio-oils from the high-moisture containing biomass. This study is to be expanded to assess the potential of biocrude upgrading in existing fossil crude oil refineries in Qatar, with an expanded economic assessment.

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